

Pilots

Three **Use Cases** will become the **real-life testbeds** for all BIMprove solutions to make sure that they will meet **industry standards!**

Fire protection with BIMprove

In building construction sites, fire can cause major complications and additional expenses and in the worst case personal damage.

Our Goal

Detect **fire hazard** and support **fire brigades**.

Fall Prevention with BIMprove

Construction sites have multiple teams working simultaneously, in many cases, not aware of each other and what the other team is doing.

Our Goal

Prevention of falling and training for workers.

Scheduling and cost benefit with BIMprove

The construction of a larger building requires complex planning.

However a wide variety of events, such as weather related work stoppages, delivery delays, etc., require ongoing rescheduling.

Our Goal

Demonstrate the **usability** of BIMprove in scheduling and cost calculations.

About

- Start date** 01 September 2020
- Duration** 36 months
- Overall Budget** € 5.593.676,25
- Topic** LC-EEB-08-2020 - Digital Building Twins (RIA)
- Key Objectives** Significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites

Team

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 958450

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Why BIMprove

BIMprove has the ambition to **revolutionize the stagnant European construction industry** and solve long-standing problems such as decreasing productivity, dangerous environment for workers, negative environmental impact and budget misalignment with real expenditures.

The Challenges

The construction market is estimated to reach over **EUR 8 billion in 2022**.

Nonetheless, the productivity is hindered by increasing costs associated with inefficiencies across the supply chain.

Progress reporting and quality checks are in most cases executed manually and without prediction methods.

Construction workers are continuously exposed to risky conditions, representing the **most dangerous sector in today's European reality**.

This has a significant influence when attracting younger generations, and satisfaction of the labour force.

This industry is highly liable in terms of resources expenditure, responsible for **40% of global energy consumption** and **38% of global greenhouse gas emissions**.

This offers a large untapped potential for cost-effective energy savings, supporting to achieve the ambitious Green Deal goals for 2050.

Our Approach

The project develops a **dynamic digital system for construction sites to fast-track productivity, cut costs and improve working conditions**.

The solution extends the 3D-based Building Information Modelling (BIM) systems with **Digital Twin Technology**, introducing a much more dynamic and multi-functional system, reliant on real-time data.

This new approach will streamline the digital transformation of the **European construction industry**, blending **Artificial Intelligence** with **AR/VR, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)** and **wearable technology**. Construction sites will have real-time information available, allowing to identify early-stage errors and being able to predict them, lowering costs and reducing risks. In addition, it will be possible to **control resources, minimizing waste and to ensure a high level of safety**.

The **core of the system is a cloud-based, data integration service**, where the **information is exchanged and data processing is possible** through modular interfaces (APIs). The interfaces can add/remove and update information in the layers.

Our Benefits

Fast-track Operations

Increase scheduling forecast capacity by 20%, automating progress & quality reporting.

Upgrade BIM models with as-built real-time data

Productivity step-up with Big Tech: AR/VR, Artificial Intelligence, Drones & Wearables

Predictive Analysis with early detection of deviations

Dowscale Costs

Reduction of costs by 20% in construction projects.

Cost Planning and Control

Budget Reliability

Faster Delivery Date

Lower Operating Costs

A Green and Safe Construction

Making the industry less exposed to labour accidents and committed to sustainability.

Continuous Safety Monitoring

Supply Chain Agility

Optimized Stockpiling

Waste Avoidance

BIMprove advocates the European Green Deal

Open and Standard

We follow an Open Innovation approach, building solutions with and for the industry

x3 Experimentation Use Cases

Contribution to Standardisation Bodies

Open Access Repository

GitHub